

Case Report

Bladder Exstrophy

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Abstract:

Bladder exstrophy, more properly, the exstrophy-epispadias complex is a rare congenital anomaly occurring once every 10,000-50,000 live births with a 2.3:1 as male & female ratio. The diagnosis involves a spectrum of anomalies of the lower abdominal wall, bladder, anterior bony pelvis and external genitalia. It occurs due to failure of the abdominal wall to close during fetal development and results in protrusion of the posterior bladder wall through the lower abdominal wall. We report a case of bladder exstrophy managed by us.

Key Words: Bladder exstrophy, Exstrophy- epispadias complex, cloacal exstrophy.

Introduction:

The exstrophy-epispadias complex of genitourinary malformations can be as simple as a glanular epispadias or an overwhelming multisystem defect such as cloacal exstrophy.

Bladder exstrophy is a rare congenital malformation of the bladder and urethra in which the bladder is turned inside out. Bladder is flattened and exposed to outside the body. Bladder neck fails to form properly and the anus and vagina appears to be displaced anteriorly. Also, there is diastasis of the pubic bones.

The incidence of bladder exstrophy has been estimated as being 1 in 10,000 to 1 in 50,000 (Lattimer & Smith, 1966) live births. The male-to-female ratio of bladder exstrophy derived from multiple series is 2.3:1 (Shapiro et al, 1984). The risk of recurrence of bladder exstrophy in a given family is approximately 1 in 100 (Ives et al, 1980).

Spectrum of anomalies

The typical manifestation of exstrophy epispadias complex is:

- Bladder everted through a midline lower abdominal wall defect
- Widening of the pubic symphysis

- Epispadias in male (dorsal cleft in the penis, exposing the urethral mucosa)
- The anus and vagina appears to be displaced anteriorly
- The testicles may not be fully descended
- Bifid clitoris in female, with a short "urethral strip" indistinguishable from bladder mucosa.

The spectrum of disease extends from spade penis and epispadias on one hand, to exstrophy with cloaca (also known as cloacal exstrophy) on the other hand.

Case report:

We report a 7 year old child presented to us for the first time with classical exstrophy of the urinary bladder. The child was second of the four siblings, born by full term normal vaginal delivery out of non consanguineous marriage, with no significant antenatal history. There was no history suggesting recurrent urinary tract infections and other noticeable illness in past. The child was of normal built and weight for his age.

Gross examination of the child showed opened bladder plate at the lower part of abdomen with urine dribbling all the time and a typical uriferous odour. Minute observations of the local area showed that the bladder mucosa is having small nodular pattern and two projections on both sides denoting the two ureteric openings (Fig.I). The bladder neck was open and could be noticed well on pulling the splayed penis downwards. There was pubic diastasis, demonstrated by pre-

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operative X-ray (Fig.II) and the testis was situated in the superficial inguinal pouch on both sides with less developed scrotal sacs. The anal opening was anteposed with short perineal distance and a normal sphincter muscle tone. Investigations of the patient revealed normal haemogram, urine analysis and renal functions.

Sonography of abdomen showed normal kidney on both the sides; both testes were seen in superficial inguinal pouch.

Surgery was planned and bladder turn-in with bladder neck reconstruction and urethroplasty(Fig.III) was done in a single sitting alongwith bilateral iliac osteotomies (Fig.IV). Repair after reconstruction was taken up very well(Fig.V) and the pubic bone approximation was demonstrated on post-operative X-ray(Fig.VI). Bilateral ureteric cannulation and bladder

Fig. I: Photograph showing bladder mucosa with small nodules. Epispadiac short penis, bilateral undescended testis with poorly developed scrotal sac, absent umbilicus.

Fig. IV: Operative picture showing exposure of iliac crest for iliac osteotomy.

Fig. II: X-ray showing wide public diastasis and bony changes in the pelvis.

Fig. V: Post-operative picture showing well formed penis and umbilicus and adequate skin closure.

Fig. III: Bladder turn-in and neck reconstruction done & ureteric catheters in situ.

Fig. VI: X-ray picture after operation showing approximation of pubic symphysis with steel wire.

drainage was done for two weeks. Post-operative course of the patient was uneventful and the patient was on follow-up for six months after surgery. During follow-up visit it was noticed that the glanuloplasty sutural disruption occurred. The child was able to hold urine for about one hour during day time. Post-operative investigation showed the bladder capacity to be approximately 50 ml with normal kidneys.

Anatomical Considerations:

Bladder exstrophy, cloacal exstrophy, and epispadias are variants of the exstrophy-epispadias complex. The cause of this complex is thought to be the failure of the cloacal membrane to be reinforced by ingrowth of mesoderm (Muecke, 1964). The cloacal membrane is a bilaminar layer situated at the caudal end of the germinal disc that occupies the abdominal wall below umbilicus. Mesenchymal ingrowth between the ectodermal and endodermal layers of the cloacal membrane results in the formation of lower abdominal muscles and pelvic bones. The cloacal membrane is subject to premature rupture; depending on the extent of the infra-umbilical defect and the stage of development during which the rupture occurs, bladder exstrophy, cloacal exstrophy, or epispadias results (Ambrose & O'Brien, 1974).

Exstrophy of the bladder is part of a spectrum of anomalies involving the urinary tract, the genital tract, the musculo-skeletal system and sometimes the intestinal tract. In classical bladder exstrophy, most anomalies are related to defects of the abdominal wall, bladder, genitalia, pelvic bones, rectum and anus.

Sponseller et al (1995) found that patients with classic bladder exstrophy have a mean 12 degree external rotation of the posterior aspect of the pelvis on each side, retroversion of the acetabulum and a mean 18 degrees of external rotation of the anterior pelvis along with 30% shortening of the pubic rami, in addition to the diastasis of the symphysis pubis.

The triangular defect caused by the premature rupture of the cloacal membrane is occupied by the exstrophy bladder and the posterior urethra. The fascial defect is limited inferiorly by the intra-symphyseal band, which represents the divergent urogenital diaphragm. This band connects the bladder neck and posterior urethra to the pubic ramus. The anterior sheath of the rectus muscle has a fan-like extension behind the urethra and bladder neck which inserts into the intra-symphyseal band.

The perineum is short and broad and the anus is situated directly behind the urogenital diaphragm; it is displaced anteriorly and corresponds to the posterior limit of the triangular fascial defect. The anal sphincter mechanism is also anteriorly displaced and it should be preserved intact in case internal urinary diversion is required in future management

Rectal prolapse frequently occurs in untreated exstrophy patients with a widely separated symphysis. It is usually transient and easily reduced. Silver et al (1997) found that the anterior corporal length of male patients with bladder exstrophy was almost 50% shorter than that of normal controls, the penis appears short not only because of the diastasis of the pubic symphysis but also because of marked congenital deficiency of anterior corporal tissue.

The vagina is shorter than normal, hardly greater than 6 cm in depth, but of normal caliber. The vaginal orifice is frequently stenotic and displaced anteriorly, the clitoris is bifid and the labia, mons pubis and clitoris are divergent. The uterus enters the vagina superiorly so that the cervix is in the anterior vaginal wall. The fallopian tubes and ovaries are normal. The frequent occurrence of indirect inguinal hernias is attributed to a persistent processus vaginalis, large internal and external inguinal rings, and lack of obliquity of the inguinal canal.

The urinary tract is usually normal, but anomalous development may occur. Horseshoe kidney, pelvic kidney, hypoplastic kidney, solitary kidney and dysplasia with megaureter are all encountered in these patients. The ureters have an abnormal course in their termination. The peritoneal pouch of Douglas between the bladder and the rectum is enlarged and unusually deep, forcing the ureter down laterally in its course across the true pelvis. The distal segment of the ureter approaches the bladder from a point inferior and lateral to the orifice and it enters the bladder with little or no obliquity. Therefore, reflux in the closed exstrophy bladder occurs in 100% of cases and subsequent surgery usually is required at the time of bladder neck reconstruction.

Discussion:

Exstrophy of bladder is a rare condition with incidence of 1 per 30,000 - 50,000 live births with male to female ratio ranging from 1.5:1 to 5:1 (Ben-Chain et al, 1996; Russell et al, 2000; De Bruyn et al, 2001). The risk of having sibling with bladder exstrophy is 1% (Silverman & Kuhn, 1993). The condition is intermediate

in severity between epispadias and cloacal exstrophy. The condition is thought to be caused by incomplete development of the infra-umbilical part of the anterior abdominal wall, associated with incomplete development of the anterior wall of the bladder owing to delayed rupture of the cloacal membrane. Persistence of the cloacal membrane prevents medial mesenchymal ingrowth, causing the abdominal wall to remain lateral and the posterior bladder wall to be exposed to the external surface (Russell et al, 2000; Gearhart & Jeffs, 1998). Trigone of the bladder and uretric openings are exposed and sometimes there is mild prolapse. The anterior abdominal wall defect involves the entire urethra and bladder neck (Silverman & Kuhn, 1993). The pubic symphysis is always widened with diastasis of rectus abdominis (De Bruyn et al, 2001). Umbilicus is low set and frequently there is omphalocele (Silverman & Kuhn, 1993; Gearhart & Jeffs, 1998) which is confluent with exstrophic bladder (Ben-Chain et al, 1996). In males the penis is short, stubby, curved upwards and is drawn into the exstrophic area, unilateral or bilateral cryptorchidism may be present and may be associated with inguinal hernia (Russell et al, 2000; Silverman & Kuhn, 1993).

In females, the urethra is short, often buried in the exstrophied bladder. The clitoris tends to be bifid. The labia are also widely separated. The vagina is short and orifice may be stenotic. Uterine prolapse or unicornuate uterus may be present (Russell et al, 2000; Silverman & Kuhn, 1993). Anus is anteriorly placed and may be patulous; this is more commonly seen in girls. Distal ends of ureters are slightly dilated and curve laterally, then medially and slightly upwards in the shape of a hook before entering the bladder (Silverman & Kuhn, 1993). In untreated patients, due to continuous dribbling of urine, there can be mucosal abrasion, infection, squamous metaplasia resulting in acquired vesico ureteric junction (VUJ) obstruction. The detrusor muscle may become fibrotic and scarred. Instances of adenocarcinoma of bladder have been reported in untreated adult patients. (Silverman & Kuhn, 1993).

Prenatal Diagnosis and Management:

Diagnosis of exstrophy - epispadias complex can be made antenatally. Antenatal ultrasonography (USG) findings (Hamada et al, 1999; Pinnette et al 1996) included:

- Repeated failure to visualize the bladder.

- Lower anterior abdominal wall mass.
- Low set umbilicus with omphalocele.
- Abnormal genitalia.
- Increased pelvic diameter.
- Associated renal anomalies, myelomeningocele and limb anomalies which are more common in cloacal exstrophy.

In neonates, exstrophy of bladder is diagnosed on clinical examination; workup includes baseline renal function test before complex reconstruction of the urinary tract. Renal USG is done to rule out renal agenesis, hydronephrosis and ectopic kidney. After bladder reconstruction is done, USG is done to look for upper urinary tract deterioration which may result from increased bladder pressure or repeated infection.

Spinal USG, radiography and MRI is done to exclude myelodysplasias or vertebral anomalies. (Gearhart & Jeffs, 1998).

An early assessment by examination under anaesthesia should be carried out in a center experienced with the condition.

Surgical Procedure:

The goals of surgery are to close the bony pelvic ring, close the bladder, posterior urethra and close the anterior abdominal wall defect and reconstruct the genitalia. In the first year of life, the bladder is closed following osteotomy of both iliac bones just lateral to sacro-iliac joint. Later reconstruction of bladder neck and sphincter is done. Complications of closure is the failure to reach adequate capacity and thus, augmentation or reconstruction may be necessary (Russell et al, 2000).

Another option is urinary diversion if continence is poor following bladder reconstruction. This can be done by ureterosigmoid anastomosis or formation of ileal conduit, colonic conduit or continent urinary diversion (Ben-Chain et al, 1996; Russell et al, 2000; De Bruyn et al, 2001). Complications include stricture at the site of anastomosis, increased chances of adenomas and adenocarcinomas at the site of ureterocolic anastomosis and hyperchloraemic acidosis (Russell et al, 2000).

In an effort to decrease costs, decrease the morbidity associated with multiple operative procedures, and possibly affect continence, there has been a recent interest in performing single-staged reconstruction or combining procedures in appropriately selected patients.

Bibliography:

1. Ambrose SS, O'Brien DP: Surgical embryology of the exstrophy-epispadias complex. *Surgical Clinics of North America*, 1974; 54: 1379-1390.
2. Ben-Chaim J, Docimo C G, Jeffs RD, Gearhart JP: Bladder exstrophy from childhood into adult life. *Journal of Royal Society of Medicine*, 1996;89 (1): 39-46.
3. De Bruyn R, Gordon I , McHugh K: Imaging of the kidneys and urinary tract in children. In: Grainger & Allison's diagnostic radiology: A textbook of Medical Imaging , (Vol. 2), 4th Edn.; Churchill Livingstone, Edinburgh, London, 2001;pp:1733- 1734.
4. Gearhart JP, Ben-Chaim J, Jeffs RD, Sanders RC: Criteria for the prenatal diagnosis of classic bladder exstrophy. *Obstetrics Gynecology*, 1995; 85: 961-964.
5. Gearhart JP, Jeffs RD : Exstrophy - Epispadias complex and bladder anomalies. In: Campbell's Urology, Patrick C. Walsh, Alan B. Retik, E. Darracott Vaughan, Jr., Alan J. Wein, (Eds.), 7th Edn.; WB Saunders, Philadelphia, 1998:1939-1990.
6. Hamada H, Takano K, Shiina H, Sakai T, Sohda S, Kubo T : New Ultrasonographic criteria for the prenatal diagnosis of Cloacal Exstrophy, *Journal of Urology*, 1999; 162(6): 2123-2124.
7. Ives E, Coffey R, Carter CO: A family study of bladder exstrophy. *Journal of Medical Genetics*, 1980;17:139-141.
8. Lattimer JK, Smith MJK: Exstrophy closure: A follow up on 70 cases. *Journal of Urology*, 1966;95:356-359.
9. Muecke EC: The role of the cloacal membrane in exstrophy: The first successful experimental study. *Journal of Urology*, 1964;92:659-667.
10. Pinette M G, Pan Y Q, Pinette S G, Stubblefield P G, Blackstone J: Prenatal diagnosis of fetal bladder and cloacal exstrophy by ultrasound. A report of three cases. *The Journal of reproductive medicine*, 1996;41(2):132-134.
11. Russell RCG, Williams N S, Bulstrode CJK: The urinary bladder: congenital defects of bladder. In: Bailey & Love, Short Practice of Surgery. 23rd Edn.; Oxford University Press, USA, 2000;pp: 1202-1203.
12. Shapiro E, Lepor H, Jeffs RD: The inheritance of classical bladder exstrophy. *Journal of Urology*, 1984;132:308-310.
13. Silverman FN, Kuhn J P: Abnormalities of pelvocaliceal system, Ureter, Bladder and Urethra. (Section 3- Epispadias – Exstrophy complex). In: Caffey's Pediatric X-ray diagnosis - An integrated approach, Mosby, Philadelphia, 1993: pp 1298 - 1301.
14. Silver RI, Yang A, Ben-Chaim J, Jeffs RD, Gearhart JP. Penile length in adulthood after exstrophy reconstruction. *Journal of Urology*, 1997;157(3):999-1003.
15. Sponseller PD, Bisson LJ, Gearhart JP, Jeffs RD, Magid & Fishman E: The anatomy of the pelvis in the exstrophy complex. *Journal of Bone Joint Surgery (American)*, 1995;77:177-189.
16. Williams DI, Keaton J: Vesical exstrophy: Twenty years' experience. *British Journal of Surgery*, 1973;60:203-207.